

‘For the Sake of Kids’: National Security and Family Values in the Ukrainian Sexuality Education Debate¹

Maryna Shevtsova²

Introduction

During the last decade (2012–2022), the idea of introducing so-called Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE) into the curriculum of Ukrainian secondary schools provoked intense political debates often covered by the media. The United Nations Population Fund defines CSE as a ‘rights-based and gender-focused approach to sexuality education, whether in school or out of school’, that is expected to include ‘scientifically accurate information about human development, anatomy, and reproductive health, as well as information about contraception, childbirth, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV’ (UN Population Fund 2021). While welcomed by some educators and policymakers, CSE faced strong resistance not only from religious groups but also from the actors that the present chapter defines as ‘heteroactivists’ and ‘heteroactivist scholars’.

Ukraine is among those countries that, thanks largely to political pressure from the European Union (EU), have, since 2012, enacted laws to prevent and eliminate discrimination, protect women from domestic violence and promote the rights of LGBTQ people. Nevertheless, these attempts at the Europeanisation of domestic gender-equality and LGBTQ policies have met opposition. For years, legislators and various political actors in Ukraine have resisted antidiscrimination legislation, either by ignoring its existence or openly opposing it. More recently, as civil society activists and international organisations have started pushing for something more than declaratory statements and insisting on the implementation of human rights legislation, opponents of gender equality and LGBTQ rights have come forward (Shevtsova 2020). Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 made the Ukrainian government rely even more on Western countries’ support, opening new opportunities for human rights activists to push for the adoption of the gender and sexual equality policies promoted by the EU. At the same time, the militarisation of society and rising nationalist spirit have created a favourable context for religious and conservative groups to advance certain ‘traditional family values’.

¹ This work was supported by Horizon 2020 Framework Programme: [Grant Number 945380].

² Maryna Shevtsova is a EUTOPIA MSCA-Cofund Postdoctoral fellow at the University of Ljubljana, Slovenia. She is also a FWO Senior Postdoctoral Fellow with the KU Leuven, Belgium. Maryna Shevtsova has a PhD in Political Science from Humboldt University, Berlin. Her research interests include LGBTQ rights, anti-gender movements in Europe, and queer migration.

According to Gacoin (2017, p.2), sexual education itself is always a ‘political project’, and a focus on the specifics and goals of the approved curriculum only serves to obscure this fact. Feminist scholars have gathered substantial evidence for the crucial role that gender plays in defining a nation’s continuous genealogy as a family construct (Norocel 2016). Women’s sexuality and motherhood, expressed in a legally sanctioned, heterosexual and strictly monogamous union with a man from the same ethnic nation, are central in this construct (Cinpoes and Norocel 2020). A successful ethno-nationalist project, therefore, would reproduce the nation while also excluding foreign influences. Along these lines, another essential part of shaping a ‘good citizen’ is an educational system, a network of institutions tasked with conveying a set of ‘proper’ national values to the country’s growing young citizens. This task is often fulfilled, as Al Ali, Tunay Altay and Katharina Galor point out in the introduction to this volume, by creating a discourse on exclusion, a myth of a heteronormative and religiously homogenous nation.

Collins and Coleman (2008, p. 281) refer to schools as a setting where home, family and community intersect; they speak of the ‘social geographies of everyday life’. Nash and Browne point out that schools are the places where children are separated from their families and teachers are responsible for making sure the children learn values and norms – ideals that may not always coincide with those of the child’s family or (religious) communities. It is no surprise, they conclude, that in many countries schools have become places that oppose any moves toward gender and sexual equalities (Nash and Browne 2021).

There is enough literature from the Western and North American context on how education becomes the channel through which the state communicates standards for ‘good citizenship’ (Gacoin 2017; Horst et al. 2020; Mitchell 2003) and provides the conditions to train a new generation of responsible citizens ready to participate in nation-building and cultural preservation. A few authors have addressed the question in Middle Eastern context, too (Ilkkaracan 2015; Sinha 2021). However, there are only a handful of studies on Central and Eastern Europe and Central Asia (Rawłuszko 2019). This chapter offers an examination of the debates around Comprehensive Sexuality Education in Ukraine in order to contribute to a better understanding of Eastern Europe’s developing opposition to LGBTQ rights. Following the research design proposed by Nash and Browne (2015), it focuses on four thematic areas – national security, the family, religion and anxieties about the safety of children. The chapter aims to explain the cultural specificities of transnational discourses that emerge in the complex Ukrainian context shaped by the vicinity of the EU, a promoter of liberal human rights values, and Russia, a self-proclaimed defender of so-called ‘traditional family values’.

I start the chapter by discussing current trends in the scholarship on the resistances to gender and sexual equalities, gender, sexuality, and nationalism and by introducing the theoretical framework and central concept of ‘heteroactivism’. I then outline the context and the methods used. The empirical section contains the analysis of a case study of the debate around the

introduction of CSE in Ukraine. I argue that local resistances, inspired by transnational networks, are still largely shaped by their local cultural and historical context. I conclude with a discussion of the implications of these findings for policymaking and questions for further research on heteroactivism and the resistance to LGBTQ rights in Eastern Europe and beyond.

<A>Schools as spaces for norms’ (re)production and resistance

Scholars seem to agree that schooling and citizenship are closely connected (Kahne et al. 2013; Keating 2016). Some see schools as an instrument to fix the problems found in the local community or society (Gorard 2010). In this view, schools are places where social norms are (re)produced, the institutions through which young citizens are ‘both controlled and disciplined by adults and within which distinct identities are (re)produced’ (Collins and Coleman 2008, p. 284). In other words, the citizenship taught in schools is not limited to what is understood as a legal political status but rather encompasses a much broader domain of everyday social and cultural life (Schuitema et al. 2018). Classrooms are spaces where a particular kind of citizen is created, ‘schooled in the norms and proper codes of behaviour related to national citizenship’ (Mitchell 2003, p. 390).

Feminist educational scholars have paid much attention to the place and role of gender in democratic schooling and to the ways in which education genders numerous areas of social interaction, including work, health, (il)legality, socioeconomic inequality and political representation (Arnot 2009; Naseem 2010). Sexuality education, more specifically, addresses a separate area of social life and presents a ‘range of pedagogical interventions with children and young people around sexualities, reproductive biology and rights, sexual health and issues concerning sexual consent and protection’ (Allred and Fox 2019, p. 670). Allred and Fox (2019, p.701) argue that CSE may ‘produce a variety of capacities that affect how bodies participate in a social context’ and that educational practices, therefore, may open up radical possibilities for becoming a citizen. Not surprisingly, as Nash and Browne (2015, p. 568) point out, schools turn into ‘contentious locations where disputes over the nature of citizenship and national values are contested through the figure of the child’.

If unravelling the micropolitics of sexuality education allows one to understand the capacities and possibilities produced by educational institutions for the process of becoming a citizen (Allred and Fox 2019, p. 670), a closer examination of the resistances to sexuality education (or to parts of it) offers us a better understanding of what kind of citizen is undesirable or what kind of citizen a child should (not) become. In this chapter, I seek to demonstrate how particular forms of (hetero)sexuality are presented as those in need of privileging and protection by the Ukrainian state, while others are deemed worthy of exclusion from the national imaginary (that is, from schools) to protect the minors – and the security of the nation.

<A>Resisting gender and sexual equalities: heteroactivism as theoretical framework

The 2010s saw a rapid growth in the body of the literature on mobilisation against gender and sexual rights in Europe and well beyond it (Kuhar and Paternotte 2017; McKay and Angotti 2013; Weiss and Bosia 2013). It soon became clear that the protests and campaigns against so-called ‘gender ideology’ should not be analysed as solely national phenomena but as one that spanned continents with numerous similarities in forms of resistances (Kuhar and Paternotte 2017, p. 4). According to the literature, there are multiple cases when local political actors choose societal homophobia as an instrument to provoke strong emotional reactions from the population and deflect attention from other issues, such as corruption or a lack of democratic progress (Shevtsova 2020; Sleptcov 2018). Weiss and Bosia (2016, p. 2–3) refer to such cases as political homophobia, a term they define as ‘a state strategy, social movement, and transnational phenomenon’ which consists of ‘the scapegoating of an “other” that drives processes of state-building and reduction... as the product of transnational influence peddling and alliances’ and a ‘part of the legitimation of political and economic power’.

While the concept of ‘political homophobia’ proves analytically useful for studies on the actions of governments and political elites, for the present study ‘heteroactivism’, a concept proposed by Browne and Nash (2017), serves as a better theoretical foundation. The authors understand ‘heteroactivism’ to refer to ‘an increasingly coordinated ideological and strategic response to LGBTQ equalities positioning “heteronormativity” (the confluence of gendered, classed, and racialised norms within man/woman divides that come together in normative heterosexual relationships) as foundational to a healthy and sustainable society’ (Browne and Nash 2017, p. 645). Browne and Nash advise viewing heteroactivism as both an ideology and as a form of activism, as the term includes various oppositions to LGBTQ equalities that are framed as the freedom of religion, protection of minors, parental rights and reproductive rights, as well as so-called gender ideologies (Browne and Nash 2017, p. 645; Kuhar and Paternotte 2017).

Heteroactivism serves the purpose of this study better since it suggests, at its core, various forms of activism and mass mobilisation based on the notion of the superiority of normative heterosexuality over all other sexualities. Importantly, in comparison with more traditional resistance to LGBTQ rights or gender equality, heteroactivism is well informed, frequently employing modern arguments for the freedom of religion and of expression, protection of minors and parental rights, among others (Nash and Browne 2021). As the empirical section will show, this is the case with Ukraine’s sexuality education debate, in which heteroactivist communities visibly progressed in creating new modes and forms of resistance. Using Ukraine as an example, this chapter demonstrates how groups, organisations and initiatives that can be defined as heteroactivist move from reactive positions to proactive ones across various spheres of public life, including education, in which heteroactivism becomes an alternative source of knowledge production.

Heteroactivism is geographically conditioned and has to be studied within a specific cultural, historical and geopolitical context. In the case of Ukraine, the transformations taking place in the

country regarding gender and sexual equality cannot be analysed without taking into consideration the country's past. For many years, Ukraine has been a battlefield between so-called 'European human rights norms' and 'traditional family values', a dominant national and foreign policy of neighbouring Russia (Shevtsova 2021, 2022). Approaching education as the channel through which the Ukrainian state communicates the standards for 'good citizenship' and provides the conditions to train a new generation of responsible citizens ready to participate in nation-building and cultural preservation, I will examine the clash between the intention to teach inclusion, diversity and multiculturalism and the intention to preserve 'traditional values', resulting in specific policies or modes of state-sanctioned discipline and surveillance. In doing so, the chapter relies on a queer feminist perspective as it strives to demonstrate how gender and sexuality, intertwined with other social conditions such as religion or nationality, have become central for understanding the 'value clashes' in Ukrainian secondary education against the background of broader (geo)political processes.

<A>Context: gender and sexual equalities in post-Euromaidan Ukraine

The development of the broader public discussion of inclusive legislation and practices regarding sexual and gender equalities in Ukraine can be traced to the early 2010s. Though Ukraine was, in the early 1990s, the first of the former Soviet republics to decriminalise homosexuality, almost no public discussion of the topics of sexual orientation, gender identity, sexual harassment, gender-based violence and comprehensive sexuality education took place until 2010–2012. Civil society organisations had dealt with these topics in Ukraine for years, but only by the 2010s, as a result of geopolitical factors, policymakers – as well as rapidly growing resistance groups – started to pay attention. On the one hand, although Ukraine has always aspired to join the European Union, since the early 2010s the EU has increased its pressure on partner countries regarding the adoption of comprehensive antidiscrimination legislation and respect for the rights of minorities and vulnerable groups and, particularly, LGBTQ rights (Slootmaeckers et al. 2016). On the other hand, pro-Russian groups have drawn more attention to the issue by creating a discursive connection between the political approximation of Ukraine and the EU and the so-called 'homosexualisation' of Ukraine. According to these groups, the EU's attempt to impose the legalisation of same-sex marriage on Ukraine contradicted the country's traditional Christian family values and even threatened national security (Shevtsova 2020; 2021).

By 2022, Ukraine – largely due to the political pressure from the EU and its member states as well as the coordinated efforts of civil society activists – has adopted several pieces of national legislation aimed at establishing sexual and gender equalities. These include an anti-discrimination law (2012), an amendment to the labour code that prohibits discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity and a law against domestic violence (2017). The years 2015 to 2021 also saw the growing visibility of LGBTQ activism. For example, in 2019 Marches of Equality took place in several major cities across the country, and by 2021 the number of officially registered LGBTQ-rights NGOs in the country exceeded forty.

At the same time, the presence of strong resistance against gender and sexual equalities prevented further progress in Ukraine and the above-mentioned legislation could not be implemented. Conservative, right-wing nationalist and religious groups (sometimes the three categories can be applied to one and the same organisation) have proven to be strong opponents of sexual and gender equalities. For example, the Ukrainian Council of Churches and Religious Organisations (UCCRO), which is the largest and one of the most prestigious nongovernmental institutions in Ukraine, remained for years one of the main forces blocking the country's ratification of the Istanbul Convention.^a The main reason for the opposition was the Convention's mention of the words 'gender', 'sexual orientation' and 'gender identity', which, according to opponents like the UCCRO, have to do with the normalisation of same-sex unions and the promotion of homosexuality. Ukraine also failed to include sexual orientation and gender identity in the list of grounds protected under its antidiscrimination law due to similar claims from various groups which opposed the measure.

The full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 led to Ukraine's growing dependence on alliances with the West and created momentum for LGBTQ and women's rights activists to advocate for new gender equality and LGBTQ rights policies. In July 2022, confirming previously expressed firm intentions to join both the EU and the NATO, the parliament of Ukraine voted for the ratification of the Istanbul Convention, despite all the protests from conservative and religious groups. Furthermore, in the summer of 2022, as the petition to establish same-sex marriage on the website of the President of Ukraine collected the 25,000 signatures necessary for the President to react, Volodymyr Zelensky promised to address this question once the war was over. In other words, it seems that the war has created certain political opportunities for LGBTQ and feminist activists.

Nevertheless, the years 2014–2021 also marked an era of renewed nationalist sentiment in Ukraine; this led, for the first time since the country's independence in 1991, to shifts in the project of nation-building and the construction of national values, a process for which educational institutions are central (Nash and Browne 2021). In 2022, as a response to the Russian aggression, these processes only strengthened and now take place against the background of society's growing militarisation. As this chapter analyses the debates around the CSE in the Ukrainian education that took place before 24 February 2022, it is too early to make any claims about which of the two factors discussed above – closer approximation with the EU and the growing influence of Western institutions this entails or the increased nationalist sentiment and militarisation and re-traditionalisation of some parts of the society – will play the major role once the war is over.

Following the reasoning of Gacoïn (2017) on the politicisation of sexual education as a nation-building project and of Nash and Browne (2021) on the influence of resistances on national policies and in shaping 'national values' and 'standards of good citizenship', I explore in this chapter nationalist grassroot and institutional resistances to sexual education in Ukrainian

schools as they were active 2019–2021. My empirical material demonstrates that in contexts that are far from being LGBTQ-friendly, sexual education shaped by oppositional ideologies can be particularly effective in establishing the notion of the ‘superiority of monogamous, binary cis-gendered, coupled marriages as best for children and for society’ (Nash and Browne 2021, p.74).

<A>**A note on method**

To examine emerging resistances to gender and sexual equalities in Ukrainian schools, I have chosen to explore the work of two major institutional actors, the Ukrainian Council of Churches and Religious Organisations (UCCRO) and the Association of Sexologists and Sexual Therapists of Ukraine (ASSU), and examine how they frame their opposition to these equalities within the broader context of the country’s cultural norms and values. I have chosen these cases as they illustrate high-profile heteroactivism in Eastern Europe generally and heteroactivism as it shapes a local, national discussion around sexual and gender equalities. While the analysis shows that there are similarities with such resistance in other countries, the core of these resistances in Ukraine is constructed according to local cultural and spatial/geopolitical specificities, as it is an opposition embedded in the national context.

In what follows, I analyse the online presence of the UCCRO and ASSU, their press releases, their official statements both on- and offline, interviews with their spokespeople and articles published between the spring of 2019 and fall of 2021. I have chosen these organisations because they produce mostly public content, make official public statements and create printed and online materials aimed at preventing the introduction of CSE in Ukrainian schools. I have chosen key documents based on their relevance, depth of argumentation and the presence of argumentative frames used throughout the organisations’ documents.

The empirical section of the chapter discusses three main frames widely used by heteroactivists to resist the introduction of CSE: protection of minors, indoctrination of the so-called ‘gender ideology’ that can lead to confusion of children and freedom of religion. As this chapter demonstrates, on the one hand these frames and arguments are very similar to those used by heteroactivists in other countries (see Nash and Browne 2021 on the UK and Canada), while on the other hand, they are embedded in a local cultural and historical context.

<A>**Two readings of sex education in Ukraine: when the name matters**

In Ukrainian, the English word ‘sex’ has at least two different translations. The first refers to biological sex, which translates into Ukrainian as ‘*stat*’, while the second – ‘*seks*’ – means sexual intercourse or sexual relations. The form of sex education that has traditionally been present in Ukraine was defined in the curriculum as ‘*statteve vykhovannia*’ – the closest translation is ‘education of sexes’. *Statteve vykhovannia* has usually been the responsibility of a biology teacher (or occasionally another teacher who volunteers) who would dedicate a separate class to the subject in the ninth grade (students are typically fourteen or fifteen years old when

they are taught human anatomy in school). The students are divided by gender and are given a forty-minute intro that usually covers the basics of contraception as well as some information on sexually transmitted infections (STIs). The teachers do not receive particular training or instruction on how to prepare for such a class, and it is normally left up to each teacher to determine how to present the class and what information to offer students. This task is usually, but not always, assigned to female teachers. According to research conducted in Ukraine in 2019 (Cedos 2019), the vast majority of teachers felt awkward and unprepared during these classes and commented that they would benefit from additional training on the topic. At the same time, this is the type of sex education accepted by the larger population, including conservative groups. Most parents, according to this same research, also expect *sttateve vykhovannia* to remain the school's responsibility. Overall, the need to have teenagers informed about contraception and STIs is not questioned or opposed by the conservative groups who contest comprehensive sexuality education.

During the past decade, however, more and more activists and civil society organisations have been trying to introduce in Ukrainian schools an approach they define as '*seksualna prosvita*'. They base this approach on the UN Population Fund's concept of comprehensive sexuality education, which is, as has been mentioned above, a 'rights-based and gender-focused approach to sexuality education, whether in school or out of school', one expected to include 'scientifically accurate information about human development, anatomy, and reproductive health, as well as information about contraception, childbirth, and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV' (UN Population Fund 2021). The initiatives to promote CSE are mostly sponsored by international and Western donor organisations and are coordinated regionally by various human rights civil society organisations usually working with women's reproductive health and/or children's rights. As I learned from the interviews and informal conversations I conducted with civil society activists and experts on sexuality education in Ukraine, the Ministry of Education and Science works closely with them, participating in discussion of the new curriculum which could possibly include CSE; however, the ministry is extremely careful not to voice opinions on the matter officially or give explicit preference to CSE over the sex education proposed by the conservative groups.

The movement 'Stop Sexual Education for Children' and the Association of Sexologists and Sexual Therapists of Ukraine (ASSU) that has launched it define the sexual education they are opposing as a 'sexual education realised through the propaganda of homosexual relations, destruction of family values and moral and ethical foundations' (ASSU 2021). ASSU clearly defines what 'properly organised sexual education (*sttateve vykhovannia*)' entails:

1. The classes should be organised separately for educators, parents, and children.
2. Children should be divided into groups according to their age. Children from different age groups cannot be mixed.

3. The curriculum must include at least twelve classes (ideally fifteen to twenty).

4. The first six to nine classes should not mention the topic of sexual intercourse.

5. The first six to nine classes must be dedicated to an ‘orientation towards couple relations, family values, friendship skills, love skills, teach[ing] how to love, show feelings [and] conscious choice of friends’.

6. Whenever physiological issues are discussed, boys and girls are to be divided into different groups.

7. An emphasis must be made on the conscious beginning of one’s sex life and the conscious and responsible choice of one’s life partner. The instructor must help the group develop an understanding of the consequences of ‘irresponsible sexual behaviour’.

8. The group should orient toward steady, monogamous relations.

At the same time, proper *statteve vykhovannia* cannot include:

1. Criticizing parents or questioning their authority.

2. Discussions of polyamory, polygamy, or other forms of ‘alternative sexual relations’.

3. The propagation of homosexual contact, since it can ‘affect the still-evolving gender identity of the child’.

4. Discussion of sexual activity in terms of purely physiological satisfaction without the centrality of couple and family relations.

5. Extensive information about the ‘sexual practices of adults’.

6. Detailed descriptions of ‘sexual deviations’.

7. Instructors who ‘irresponsibly provide contraceptives as the one and main protection against STDs and HIV’.^b

For heteroactivists in Ukraine, too, school is supposed to be a safe space for children (Nash and Browne 2021) where the ‘natural’ dominance of heterosexuality and cisgenderism is conveyed to the children with no chance of their ‘indoctrination’ with foreign values or the ‘propagation’ of homosexuality or ‘alternative forms of sexuality’. The danger of the normalisation of non-heterosexual relations and sexualities for minors is at the core of most heteroactivist claims, both those of scholars and religious institutions such as the UCCRO. The ‘neutral’ and ‘objective’ knowledge that the school is expected to offer children is inherently heteronormative and prioritises abstinence as a method for contraception and protection against STIs. There is no

assumption that heteronormativity can be or is imposed on children; it is presented as the only 'healthy' norm that they should be taught. No other forms of sexual orientation and gender identity are supposed to be mentioned in such classes, and while LGBTQ people can be mentioned during other courses (as a part of those courses' curricula), their 'lifestyle' should not be presented as normal or discussed in detail, so as not to 'confuse' minors.

<A>**Protecting minors: for the sake of the kids**

The heteroactivist ideology in Ukraine is predominantly built around the theme of protecting minors. School, in this picture, is a place where children are separated from their parents and become vulnerable to multiple possible influences which must be controlled to ensure their safety as minors. The educational content the children receive thus corresponds to the general idea of what it means to be a good citizen of their country.

With regard to sexuality education, two central issues of heteroactivist resistance are sex as a source of pleasure – and its possibility outside the family (that is, the marriage of a heterosexual couple) – and non-heteronormative sexualities.

CSE is seen by heteroactivists, UCCRO and ASSU as 'experiments on children' that are beyond their families' control and are aimed at promoting 'gender ideology' in schools. This ideology, in their rhetoric, gives children the 'wrong' ideas about what sexuality is supposed to mean in their lives as well as which sexualities are societally-approved and state-sanctioned and which are deviant and unacceptable. In their publications, heteroactivists refer to alleged research results which would prove that Western countries with more 'liberal' approaches to sexuality education have higher rates of 'gender deviations' as well as suicide and depression among teenagers (Rebro 2019). The children, therefore, must be protected against such harmful influences, and schools must become a 'safe space that makes impossible imposing on children the idea of "normalcy" of homosexuality and other sexual deviations' (Urazbayeva 2020).

Another argument commonly pops up in discussions about the need to protect the 'majority' of the children against those who 'think' they might be a part of the LGBTQ community. Since heteroactivists reject the very idea of LGBTQ children, they first claim that such children often wish for things that may not be the best for them. If their parents do not want to stimulate 'psychological deviations in children' they should understand that 'harmonious development of a child is not equal to fulfilling all their wishes'. Second, they claim that one cannot 'take care of some children by ignoring or offending the others'. Giving trans children safe access to schools, in other words, endangers the safety of other children and should, therefore, not be allowed (Gorgota 2020).

These arguments are incorporated into the larger discourse on the importance of the traditional Christian family to Ukrainian society: gender ideology, hidden within comprehensive sexual

education, is aimed at ruining ‘family foundations’ and imposing foreign liberal ideology on children – who are, after all, future citizens.

<A>Teaching third gender? On ‘gender ideologies’ in schools

Gender confusion, or introducing a ‘new’ or ‘third’ gender, is among the most popular argument against CSE in schools. In August 2021, Ukraine’s Ministry of Education and Science announced plans to conduct a gender audit of schools nationwide. This provoked a strong reaction from conservative groups; in particular, the UCCRO published an official appeal to the president of Ukraine asking him to withdraw from the international Biarritz Partnership for Gender Equality (UCCRO 2020). Being part of the Biarritz Partnership required the government to take multiple steps toward achieving comprehensive gender equality, including in the sphere of education. In its appeal to the president, the UCCRO alleged that the Western countries which founded the partnership interpret gender equality not as the absence of discrimination against a person on the basis of gender but in such a way as to introduce a ‘gender ideology’ normalizing the concept that people independently choose their gender according to their will (UCCRO 2020).

Similar to the case of British and Canadian schools described by Nash and Browne (2021), Ukrainian heteroactivists opposing sexuality education and ‘gender ideology’ frame those as confusing for the majority of the children, challenging the societal ‘norms’ and threatening the ‘healthy’ order of things. The psyche of children is presented as fragile and prone to persuasion: a child can be ‘convinced’ that their sexual orientation is not heterosexual or their gender identity is different from the one assigned at birth.

Official resources from the UCCRO and ASSU contain quite a few articles discussing foreign examples of creating LGBTQ-inclusive school environments – or role models for fighting them. For example, the webpage of *Vseukrayinski Sobor* (the online portal of the Orthodox Christian Church in Ukraine) has a section titled ‘Threats and Challenges’ where foreign countries’ cases are regularly discussed. One of those articles, ‘In Scotland one can become transgender at the age of four’, discusses the attempts to create a safe and healthy school environment for trans kids in Scotland. In particular, the article is concerned with the consequences that teachers might face if they question the gender ‘chosen’ by a child. Heteroactivists fear that ‘the Church’ will be driven out of schools, which will turn schools into spaces where a child’s gender and sexuality can be ‘shaped’ in an undue manner. They refer to such an inclusive school environment as a ‘mechanism that will forbid parents of a child making decisions about recognizing their child’s gender’ (Vseukrayinski Sobor 2021). According to another article on the portal, LGBTQ teenagers do not exist because sexuality is defined as beginning in one’s early- to mid-twenties. In other words, heteroactivist opponents of CSE and LGBTQ-inclusive schools on the one hand reject the fact that a child *can* have a non-heterosexual orientation or non-cisgender identity. On the other hand, they present children’s sexuality and gender as something fluid and vulnerable enough to be easily confused by the wrong guidance and changed against the will of their

parents. The new kind of school, that is, one tolerant and friendly toward LGBTQ children, is seen as an institution that opposes the ‘normal’ family and indoctrinates students with values and norms imposed by the West.

Heteroactivists claim that they do not oppose measures to prevent gender discrimination if it means fighting gender-based violence or ensuring equal rights for men and women. Instead, they argue that a broader reading of the concept of gender contains a set of confusing ideas which can adversely affect minors. A closer reading of their texts, however, shows that these groups do not fully supported gender equality either; they often refer to the importance of following ‘traditional gender role models’, understanding the differences between men and women and paying attention to ‘natural’ and ‘biological’ characteristics of the two genders.

To summarise, in addition to the danger of presenting sex as a source of pleasure and something beyond simply a means to procreate in a heteronormative monogamous relationship, heteroactivists in Ukraine oppose CSE as a danger that plants seeds of gender confusion in children. Traditional gender norms and the duality of gender/biological sex, according to them, are to be carefully shaped and protected by parents and by the school – where the Church should be present. These heteroactivists do accept, in other words, that gender norms may differ from the norms that they promote, but since they privilege heterosexuality and heteronormativity as the only norms good for society, their work is aimed at protecting and reaffirming those values.

<A>**Protecting families – protecting the nation**

As they see education as the process of creating new docile citizens (Thapan 2006), heteroactivist organisations view what they consider to be the attempts of foreign states or institutions to interfere with existing policies or to change practices (or introduce CSE) as a threat to the nation’s survival. I have already mentioned the strong association in public discourse between Ukraine’s approximation with the European Union and the import of certain values and norms, such as same-sex marriage and, in general, inclusion for LGBTQ people. Heteroactivists refer to attempts to promote these norms as a threat to the safety and even survival of the nation, while framing their own resistance as national defence. They rely not only the notion that minors have vulnerable psyches – and are thus easy to confuse and push toward ‘changing gender’ – but the fear that the whole nation will stop reproducing itself due to ‘gender ideology’.

In their materials, heteroactivists mention particular international institutions and organisations that threaten Ukrainian national security. One of these is the United Nations Fund for Population Activities (UNFPA), which develops the promotion of CSE in Ukraine. *Vseukrayinski Sobor* mentions several events organised by UNFPA that are in some way related to LGBTQ rights, normalised homosexual relations or the human rights of HIV-positive people. These events, according to the authors, reveal the true ideological position of UNFPA. UNFPA’s promotion of women’s rights serves, according to the ASSU, as a ‘Trojan horse’ which will ‘bring inside the

society [foreign] values and norms' (ASSU 2020). Furthermore, joining international initiatives such as the Istanbul Convention or Biarritz Partnership is seen as 'creating a powerful mechanism to introduce gender ideology and punish those who oppose it' (Ibid.).

The solution, according to heteroactivists, is in their resistances, and ultimately in appealing to the government to withdraw from the international obligations that disrupt traditional educational practices and threaten Ukrainian families and the Ukrainian nation. Otherwise, according to the UCCRO, the consequence would be the following:

<EXT> We see examples of other countries where the people did not stand up for the education of their children. We see that the spiritual and pro-family curriculum has been replaced by sexuality education for first grade, where from the very beginning children are being offered what is called 'education' but, in fact, is propaganda of masturbation, sexual experiments, various sexual deviations, LGBT, transgenderism, gender change, etc.
</EXT> (Vseukrayinski Sobor 2020)

The heteroactivist discourse, therefore, encourages resistance in three realms: the private, family realm, where parents and families should have control over their children's sexualities (as long as those are heterosexual families that accept heteronormativity); school, where the Church is crucial in opposing children's confusion and the potential normalisation of 'wrong' sexualities; and the state and public realm, where the government is expected to protect national security by ensuring that only certain sexualities and gender identities are recognised as 'proper'.

<A>Conclusion

In the present article, I argue that between 2019–2021, Ukrainian classrooms and school curricula turned into a battleground for so-called heteroactivist groups, who resist the promotion of gender and sexual equalities in the country. In their resistances to CSE, and, broadly speaking, against gender and sexual equality, they stress the superiority of heteronormative sexualities and gender identities over all others, and use this argument to reaffirm social and political inequalities already existing in the Ukrainian society. Applying both transnationally-inspired and locally-embedded frames and arguments, oppositions presented by religious groups and groups of scholars built an organised resistance to the 'threat' of 'alternative forms of sexuality and gender identity'. Through the framework of heteroactivism, I explored here how monogamous, cisgender heterosexuality is presented as something in need of protection and promotion for the sake of the health and even survival of the nation through the protection and correct education of children (minors). This protection is to be granted by the state and can only be institutionalised when the state and Church define both public and private spheres (foundations of the family).

The analysis of two cases – the Ukrainian Council of Churches and Religious Organisations (UCCRO) and the Association of Sexologists and Sexual Therapists of Ukraine (ASSU) – confirms the claim of Browne and Nash (2017; 2021) that heteroactivism is 'inherently

geographical' but transnationally inspired. Indeed, one can see multiple similarities between the arguments, forms of mobilisation and strategies of resistance used by heteroactivists in Ukraine and elsewhere, including the cases of the UK and Canada analysed by the authors. The discussion around sexual and gender freedoms in Ukrainian schools is rooted in geopolitical situations, that is, the ideological clash between the so-called traditional family values – promoted by pro-Russian groups and some religious groups funded by the US – and the vaguely defined 'European values', which are supposed to include sexual and gender equalities and, in particular, LGBTQ rights. Leaving behind notions of 'sin' or 'sexual deviation', the opponents now make central to their claim the idea of children's rights and parental control over what their children are taught in school. Securing the 'safety' of school/classroom spaces from 'foreign gender ideology' becomes the specific challenge for Ukrainian heteroactivists.

It is worth noting that unlike in some other cases, the topics of race and ethnicity are largely absent from this discussion, even though implicitly the idea of a 'Ukrainian' family is heterosexual, Orthodox or Greek-Catholic Christian and white. Indeed, the right-wing groups in Ukraine, as in some other Central Eastern European countries, choose non-white Ukrainians for their attacks; nevertheless, this theme is largely overlooked not only by the rest of the opponents of gender and sexual equalities in the country but also by the activists promoting CSE. The common myth that there is no such thing as racism and xenophobia in Ukraine has penetrated this sphere as well.

While the topic of opposition to LGBTQ rights in Central and Eastern Europe has recently gained increased attention (Luciani 2021; Shevtsova 2022), this work stresses the further need to examine resistances to 'progressive' sexuality education that is supposed to be LGBTQ-friendly and supportive. Eastern European countries like Ukraine differ in many aspects regarding their legislation and implementation of LGBTQ-rights norms and policies, as even at earlier stages of adoption, actors can imitate or adjust to their local context both the best practices for promotion of and for resistance against sexual and gender equalities. Considering this peculiarity, one needs to employ both geographical (spatiality) and geopolitical (politics, history and culture) lenses to deal with the implications of these new (hetero)activisms. Similar to the cases in other locations, as Kandiyoti argues in her chapter in this volume, the fight over CSE in Ukrainian schools is shaped by an external, geopolitical clash of values and powers in Europe as well as by internal national political dynamic.

Russia's war in Ukraine, which escalated with the full-scale invasion on 24 February 2022, has made situation of gender equality promotion and LGBTQ rights in Ukraine even more complex by amplifying the controversial trends of closer approximation with the EU and increasing nationalist sentiment and militarisation of society. The year 2022 brought substantial changes to both the legislation and societal attitudes towards sexual and gender equality. In addition to the adoption of LGBTQ-friendly legislation, such as the Istanbul Convention and the law prohibiting homophobic and transphobic hate speech, sociologists reported growing support for such issues

as marriage equality for same-sex couples or the political participation of women (NDI 2023). The most recent polls also show decreasing popular trust in the Church (from 55 to 44%) and growing trust in the government (from 14 to 52%) (UNIAN 2023); this change, too, can play a favourable role in the promotion of CSE in Ukrainian secondary education.

Nevertheless, the militarisation of society, economic crisis, rise of radical nationalism and increased social inequalities can lead to a growth of conservative attitudes and cementing of traditional gender roles in some regions of the country. Both ASSU and UCCRO have continued their work with the population in 2022–2023, staying firm in their opposition to gender and sexual equality. While sexuality education at schools is not central to the current debates around schooling in Ukraine, it is inevitable that this clash of values will, in the future, influence the state of Ukrainian secondary education and shape the place of gender and sexuality in it.

<A>References

Allred, P. and N.J. Fox (2019) ‘Assembling citizenship: Sexualities education, micropolitics and the becoming-citizen’, *Sociology*, 53(4), pp. 689–706. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038518822889> [accessed 07 February 2023].

Arnot, M. (2009) *Educating the gendered citizen: Sociological engagements with national and global agendas*. London: Routledge.

ASSU (*Asotsiatsiya Seksolohiv ta Seksoterapevtiv Ukrayiny*) (2021) ‘*Stop seksualnu osvitu v Ukraini* (Stop sexual education in Ukraine)’, ASSU. Available from: <https://sexology.org.ua/stop-seksualna-osvita-v-ukraini/> [accessed 07 February 2023].

ASSU (*Asotsiatsiya Seksolohiv ta Seksoterapevtiv Ukrayiny*) (2020) ‘*Rozbudova simyi pid mizhnarodnym kontrolem* (Family building under the international control)’, ASSU. Available from: <https://sexology.org.ua/rozbudova-sim-i-pid-mizhnarodnim-kontrolem/> [accessed 2 August 2023].

Browne, K. and C. Nash (2017) ‘Heteroactivism: Beyond anti-gay’, *ACME: An International Journal for Critical Geographies*, 16(4), pp. 643–652. Available at: <https://acme-journal.org/index.php/acme/article/view/1631> [accessed 07 February 2023].

Cedos (2019) ‘*Seksualna osvita v shkoli: chy ye scho pokraschuvaty?* (Sexuality education at schools: is there a room for improvement?)’, Cedos. Available from: <https://cedos.org.ua/researches/stvorennia-peredumov-dlia-rozvytku-seksualnoi-osvity-v-shkolakh/> [accessed 07 February 2023].

Cinpoes, R.P. and O.C. Norocel (2020) ‘Nostalgic nationalism, welfare chauvinism, and migration anxieties in Central and Eastern Europe’ in Norocel, O.C., A. Hellström and

- M.B. Jørgensen (eds.) *Nostalgia and hope: Intersections between politics of culture, welfare, and migration in Europe*. Cham: Springer, pp. 51–65.
- Collins, D. and T. Coleman (2008) ‘Social geographies of education: Looking within, and beyond, school boundaries’, *Geography Compass*, 2(1), pp. 281–299. doi: doi.org/10.1111/j.1749-8198.2007.00081.x.
- Gacoin, A. (2017) ‘Encountering gender: Resisting a neo-liberal political rationality for sexuality education as an HIV prevention strategy’, *Gender and Education*, 29(1), pp. 66–83. doi: doi.org/10.1080/09540253.2016.1197378.
- Gorard, S. (2010) ‘Education can compensate for society—a bit’, *British Journal of Educational Studies*, 58(1), pp. 47–65. doi: doi.org/10.1080/00071000903516411.
- Gorgota, O. (2020) ‘*Genderna dysphoriya u pidlitka: pryymaty chy ne pryymaty* (Gender dysphoria of teenagers; to accept or not to accept)’, ASSU. Available from: <https://sexology.org.ua/genderna-disforiya-u-pidlitka-prijmati-chi-ne-prijmati/> [accessed 05 February 2023].
- Horst, C., M. Bivand Erdal and N. Jdid (2020) ‘The “good citizen”: asserting and contesting norms of participation and belonging in Oslo’, *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 43(16), pp. 76–95. doi: doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2019.1671599.
- Ilkharacan P. (2015). ‘Commentary: Sexual health and human rights in the Middle East and North Africa: progress or backlash?’, *Global Public Health*, 10(2), pp. 268-70. doi: 10.1080/17441692.2014.986173.
- Kahne, J., D. Crow and N. Lee (2013) ‘Different pedagogy, different politics: High school learning opportunities and youth political engagement’, *Political Psychology*, 34(3), pp. 419–441. doi: doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9221.2012.00936.x.
- Keating, A. (2016) ‘Educating tomorrow’s citizens: What role can schools play?’, *Foro de Educación*, 14(20), pp. 35–47. doi: dx.doi.org/10.14516/fde.2016.014.020.004.
- Kuhar, R. and D. Paternotte (eds.) (2017) *Anti-gender campaigns in Europe: Mobilizing against equality*. Lanham, MA: Rowman and Littlefield.
- Luciani, L. (2021) ‘Where the Personal is (Geo)Political: Performing Queer Visibility in Georgia in the Context of EU Association’, *Problems of Post-Communism*, 70(2), pp. 197–208. doi: doi.org/10.1080/10758216.2021.1937228.

- McKay, T. and N. Angotti (2016) 'Ready Rhetorics: Political Homophobia and Activist Discourses in Malawi, Nigeria, and Uganda', *Qualitative Sociology* 39, pp. 397–420. doi: doi.org/10.1007/s11133-016-9342-7.
- Mitchell, K. (2003) 'Educating the national citizen in neoliberal times: From the multicultural self to the strategic cosmopolitan', *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 28(4), pp. 387–403. Available from: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3804388> [accessed 07 February 2023].
- Naseem, M. (2010) *Education and Gendered Citizenship in Pakistan*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Nash, C.J. and K. Browne (2021) 'Resisting the mainstreaming of LGBT equalities in Canadian and British Schools: Sex education and trans school friends', *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space*, 39(1), pp. 74–93. doi: doi.org/10.1177/2399654419887970.
- Nash, C.J. and K. Browne (2015) 'Best for society? Transnational opposition to sexual and gender equalities in Canada and Great Britain', *Gender, Place & Culture*, 22(4), pp. 561–577. doi: doi.org/10.1080/0966369X.2014.885893.
- NDI (2023) 'NDI January 2023 Poll: Opportunities and Challenges Facing Ukraine's Democratic Transition', NDI. Available from: <https://www.ndi.org/publications/ndi-january-2023-poll-opportunities-and-challenges-facing-ukraines-democratic> [accessed 06 March 2023].
- Norocel, C.O. (2016) 'Disciplinary intersections of gender and ethnicity in populist radical right media in Romania', *Identities*, 23(2), pp. 247–264. doi: doi.org/10.1080/1070289X.2015.1054394.
- Rawłuszko, M. (2019) 'And if the opponents of gender ideology are right? gender politics, Europeanization, and the democratic deficit', *Politics & Gender*, 17(2), pp. 301–323. doi: doi.org/10.1017/S1743923X19000576.
- Rebro, D. (2019) 'Korol-to goliy: 5 myfiv pro transgendernist (A naked king: five myths about transgenders)', *Khrystyany dlya Ukrainy*. Available from: <http://c4u.org.ua/5-myths-about-transsexuality/> [accessed 07 February 2023].
- Schuitema, J., H. Radstake, J. van de Pol and W. Veugelers (2018) 'Guiding classroom discussions for democratic citizenship education', *Educational Studies*, 44(4), pp. 377–407. doi: doi.org/10.1080/03055698.2017.1373629.
- Shevtsova, M. (2022) 'Religion, Nation, State, and Anti-Gender Politics in Georgia and Ukraine', *Problems of Post-Communism*, 70(2), pp. 163–174. doi: doi.org/10.1080/10758216.2022.2085581.

- Shevtsova, M. (2021) *LGBTI politics and value change in Ukraine and Turkey: Exporting Europe?* London: Routledge.
- Shevtsova, M. (2020) ‘Fighting “Gayropa”: Europeanization and Instrumentalization of LGBTI Rights in Ukrainian Public Debate’, *Problems of Post-Communism*, 67(6), pp. 500–510. doi: doi.org/10.1080/10758216.2020.1716807.
- Sinha, T. (2021). ‘Observing the Cultural Differences in Young Women Living in the United States and the UAE Through the Administration of Sexual Education’, *The Undergraduate Journal of Public Health at University of Michigan*, 5. doi: doi.org/10.3998/ujph.17872072.0005.004
- Sleptcov, N. (2018) ‘Political Homophobia as a state strategy in Russia’, *Journal of Global Initiatives: Policy, Pedagogy, Perspective*, 12(1), pp. 140–161. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.kennesaw.edu/jgi/vol12/iss1/9> [accessed 07 February 2023].
- Slootmaeckers, K., H. Touquet and P. Vermeersch (eds.) (2016) *The EU enlargement and gay politics: The impact of eastern enlargement on rights, activism, and prejudice*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Thapan, M. (2006) “‘Docile’ Bodies, ‘Good’ Citizens or ‘Agential’ Subjects? Pedagogy and Citizenship in Contemporary Society”, *Economic and Political Weekly*, 41(39), pp. 4195–4203. Available from: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4418762> [accessed 07 February 2023].
- UCCRO (2020) *Ukrainian Council of Churches warns on some Biarritz Partnership goals*. Available from: <https://vrciro.org.ua/en/news/uccro-statement-on-g7-biarritz-partnership-agenda> [accessed 05 February 2023].
- UNIAN (2023) ‘*Dovira Ukrayinciv do cerkvy padaye, a do ZSU zrosla mayzhe do 100: opytuvannya* (The trust of Ukrainians toward the Church is falling and towards the Military Forces of Ukraine has increased to almost 100: a survey)’, UNIAN. Available from: <https://www.unian.ua/society/dovira-ukrajinciv-do-cerkvi-padaye-a-do-zsu-zrosla-mayzhe-do-100-opituvannya-12107976.html> [accessed 06 March 2023].
- UN Population Fund (2021) *Comprehensive sexuality education*, UNFPA. Available from: <https://www.unfpa.org/comprehensive-sexuality-education> [accessed 07 February 2023].
- Urazbayeva, A. (2020) ‘*Problemy Ukrayinskoyi shkoly, pro yaki nikhto ne govoryt* (Problems of Ukrainian school nobody talks about)’, ASSU. Available from: <https://sexology.org.ua/problemi-ukrainskoi-shkoli-pro-yaki-nihto-ne-govorit/> [accessed 07 February 2023].

Vseukrayinski Sobor (2021) ‘*U Shotlandii mozna staty transgenderom z chotyryoh rokiv* (One can become transgender in Scotland at the age of four)’, Vseukrayinski Sobor. Available from: <https://sobor.com.ua/news/stati-transgenderom-z-4-rokiv#> [accessed 07 February 2023].

Vseukrayinski Sobor (2020) ‘*Uryad skhvalyv priyednannya do partnerstva Biarritz* (The government approved joining Biarritz partnership)’, Vseukrayinski Sobor. Available from: <https://sobor.com.ua/news/uryad-skhvaliv-priyednannya-do-partnerstva-biarric> [accessed 07 February 2023].

Weiss, M.L. and M.J. Bosia (eds.) (2013) *Global homophobia: states, movements, and the politics of oppression*. Champaign, IL: University of Illinois Press

<A>Notes

^a The Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence, or the Istanbul Convention, is a human rights treaty. The document was opened for signature on 11 May 2011, in Istanbul, Turkey. The goal of the Convention is to prevent gender-based violence, protect victims and end the impunity of perpetrators. Ukraine signed the Convention in November 2011 but as of September 2021 had failed to ratify it.

^b This list is taken from the Ukrainian version provided on the Association’s official website. I translated it into English, closely adhering to the original text, and chose to place in quotation marks some phrases to stress that they are word-to-word translations. Original in Ukrainian at <https://sexology.org.ua/stop-seksualna-osvita-v-ukraini/>, accessed on 6 August 2021.